

AI-Powered Mental Health Support for Undergraduates

Tharapathi K.M.G.D^{1*}, Aththanayaka A.M.I.P², Disanayaka N.D³, Fernando W.G.Y⁴

¹Faculty of Information Technology, Horizon Campus, Malabe, Sri Lanka.

Abstract

University students in Sri Lanka face a range of persistent mental health issues arising from social pressures, financial difficulties, and academic stress. Due to social stigma, the high cost of professional counselling, and limited access to help, many undergraduates are reluctant to seek professional counselling even when they are faced with such issues. Providing accessible, affordable, and privacy-preserving mental health support with artificial intelligence can increase the effectiveness of addressing these issues. This study presents an AI-powered mobile application that helps university students in Sri Lanka manage their stress and anxiety. The application provides personalized emotional support through chat-based interactions, mindfulness exercises, mood tracking, motivational content, and stress-relieving games, all of which are integrated with Sinhala language data and the LLaMA large language model. By incorporating Sinhala and Natural Language Processing (NLP), the app ensures that content is delivered in an emotionally and culturally sensitive manner while protecting user privacy. By providing localized AI-driven mental health support, the proposed solution seeks to reduce barriers to help, encourage early intervention, and increase students' resilience.

Keywords: *AI, Chatbots, Mental Health, Undergraduate, Sinhala.*